

Enlightenment on the Edge: Mozart, Goethe, Mayr, and the Illuminati—Music and Secret Societies in the Late Eighteenth Century

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Abstract

This paper explores the little-known history of the Bavarian Illuminati's activities in Valtellina during the last decades of the eighteenth century. Drawing on archival sources and contemporary accounts, it reconstructs the networks of secret lodges, clandestine printing presses, and musical societies—including those connected to major cultural figures such as Goethe and Mozart—that challenged the authority of Church and State in this Alpine borderland. Special attention is given to the roles of Francesco Tommaso Maria De Bassus and Johann Simon Mayr, the circulation of forbidden Enlightenment literature, and the revolutionary use of opera and satire as tools of propaganda.

The article devotes particular focus to the influence and reinterpretation of Mozart's *Die Zauberflöte* (*The Magic Flute*) and Goethe's works, especially his "enlightened" phase and *Die Leiden des jungen Werthers* (*The Sorrows of Young Werther*), showing how these masterpieces resonated with—and helped shape—the radical cultural ferment of Valtellina. The impact of their ideas, and the ways in which they were referenced and reimagined by the Illuminati and their networks, are explored in detail.

The study sheds new light on the spread of radical Enlightenment thought in Northern Italy, the intersections between Freemasonry, the Illuminati, and the artistic avant-garde, and the intellectual battles that influenced both local and European history. Some passages reflect the strong language and anti-clerical stance of the time, providing unique insight into this era of creative and ideological upheaval.

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1. Introduction

A cultural and political movement linked to the secret Order of the Bavarian Illuminati can be traced in Valtellina—a remote Alpine valley in northern Italy, bordering Switzerland—during the last two decades of the eighteenth century. The Society of the Illuminati was founded in Ingolstadt on May 1st, 1776, the very same year as the American Declaration of Independence. From the very beginning, it consciously positioned itself against absolutism and organized religions. Its founder was Adam Weishaupt, a professor of canon law at the University of Ingolstadt, who, despite his position, was an atheist and a materialist. His aim was to restore to mankind the natural freedom he saw as limited by traditional political and religious forces. For this reason, he adopted the secret name "Spartacus," after the leader of the slave revolt.

From its very foundation, the Order of the Illuminati aimed to build a European network: alongside Weishaupt, Baron Francesco Tommaso Maria De Bassus acted as the operative mastermind for Italy and Switzerland, concentrating the core of the movement precisely in the area between Poschiavo—a mountain town now in Switzerland—and Valtellina. A co-founder of the Illuminati and Weishaupt's right-hand man, De Bassus adopted the secret name "Hannibal." Living in Valtellina, he turned Poschiavo (just north of Tirano, on the Italian-Swiss border) into the Italian laboratory of the sect. From there, he preached equality, freedom, and a return to the state of nature, envisioning a grand society founded on goodness and peace.

The ritual texts of the Bavarian Illuminati, specifically for the degree of Epopte—one of the thirteen ranks in their hierarchy, a term borrowed from ancient Greek mystery cults meaning "one who has seen" or "the initiate"—drew heavily on Rousseau's theory that man is naturally good. During meetings, in the presence of already initiated brethren, the Illuminati president would state that "the human race also has its own childhood, youth, maturity, and old age. In each of these periods, people experience new needs. From this arise their moral and political revolutions. In maturity, the full dignity of humanity is manifested. Only then, after a long experience, does man realize how unfortunate it is to violate the rights of others and to take advantage of certain outward benefits to elevate himself at the expense of others. Only in this stage does one see and understand what a good and honorable thing it is to be human. This earliest age belongs to rough and wild nature. The family forms society. Hunger and thirst are easily satisfied; shelter from the elements, a woman, and rest after labor are the only needs of this period. In such a state, man enjoyed two of the greatest blessings: equality and freedom. He enjoyed them fully, and would always have enjoyed them, had he chosen to follow the path indicated by Nature. Happy mortals!" [1]

According to Weishaupt, therefore, man should find within himself the prototype of unspoiled Nature, eliminating the dross and trappings of civilization.

"The Association of which I have been speaking, is the Order of Illuminati, founded in 1775 (sic) by Dr. Adam Weishaupt, professor of Canon law in the University of Ingolstadt, and abolished in 1786 by the Elector of Bavaria, but revived immediately after, under another name, and in a different form, all over Germany. It was again detected and seemingly broken up; but it had by this time taken so deep root that it still subsists without being detected and has spread into all the countries of Europe" [2].

Born in Ingolstadt (a city in Bavaria, southern Germany) on February 6, 1748, Weishaupt approached Catholicism in 1753, following the teaching of Baron Johann Adam Ickstatt, who directed him toward the Jesuit College. Ickstatt had been curator of the University of Ingolstadt since 1742, holding the post until 1765, when he retired and Weishaupt gained access to his private library. Through this, he also became interested in French philosophical works, especially those by Rousseau and Voltaire. The latter (Voltaire) held radical views, as demonstrated in a letter to Frederick II: "Finally, when the body of the Church is sufficiently weakened and unbelief is strong enough, the decisive blow will be struck with the sword of a complete and endless persecution. A reign of terror will dominate the earth and continue until any Christian is so obstinate as to adhere to Christianity." [1]

Weishaupt may well have drawn his aim of destroying the Jesuits and the Church directly from Voltaire and the Encyclopedists. He graduated from the University of Ingolstadt in 1768. He worked as a tutor for four years before being promoted to assistant. According to Weishaupt, one's goals must be pursued by any means

necessary and in complete secrecy: “Each initiate is told to bring a friend. This is done in order to form a legion, which, even more than the Theban Legion, is to be called holy and invincible.” [1] He awakened in his followers the desire for equality and freedom, making them indifferent to governments. He led men from different nations and religions into a common bond, drawing the brightest minds away from the Church and the State. In doing so, he undermined the very foundations of the States.

These ideas were still moderate, because for the higher ranks of “Magicians” and “Men-Kings,” everything was considered matter. “How many prejudices have we not found to destroy in you,” Weishaupt would preach, “before we managed to convince you that this so-called religion of Christ was nothing more than the work of priests, imposture, and tyranny? If this is the Gospel so widely proclaimed and admired, what should we think of all other religions? Know then that they all have the same origin in fictions and are founded on lies, error, and imposture... God and the world are one and the same; all religions are inconsistent, chimerical, and inventions of ambitious men.” [1]

Each initiate was given a pseudonym—a secret name or *nom de guerre*—on which he was asked to reflect, and which, according to the leaders, summed up the character and mission of the candidate. The Illuminati were divided into two social classes, which constituted the “lower structure” and the “upper structure” of the Order, comprising a total of thirteen degrees. One structure served as preparation for the other and had, as its apparent purpose, a return to the Christianity of the origins, freeing the initiate from prejudice through the study of authors such as Plutarch, Seneca, and Helvetius.

The lower structure was divided into nine degrees; the first four constituted the Novitiate: Novice, Minerval, Lesser Illuminatus, and Greater Illuminatus. Next came Apprentice, Fellow, and Master—the three Symbolic Degrees also found in Freemasonry—and finally, the two Scottish Degrees: Scottish Novice and Scottish Knight or Director Illuminatus.

The lower structure had a pedagogical aim, as Weishaupt wrote on March 5, 1778, to Xavier von Zwack (who in the Order had taken the name Filippo Strozzi—like Mazzini—and later that of Cato), because men, as he wrote, “if they become politicians before they learn morality, they become scoundrels.”

The true mysteries were reserved for the upper structure, which was divided into the Lesser Mysteries—Epopete or Illuminated Priest, and Regent or Illuminated Prince—and the Greater Mysteries: Philosophical Magus and Man-King.

In the instructions for the grade of Regent, Weishaupt required the Illuminati “to hide themselves under the guise of another society.” [1] The lower lodges of Freemasonry, as the code states, “are meanwhile the most convenient veil for our great purpose, because the world is already accustomed not to expect anything great or worthy of attention from the Freemasons.” [1] It took its first rise among the Free Masons, but is totally different from Free Masons. It was not, however, the mere protection gained by the secrecy of the Lodges that gave occasion to it, but it arose naturally from the corruptions that had gradually crept into that fraternity, the violence of the party-spirit which pervaded it, and from the total uncertainty and darkness that hangs over the whole of that mysterious association [3].

Illuminatism [4] and Freemasonry are therefore two distinct phenomena: they can coexist but should not be confused.

Why would the Illuminati have chosen a secret Masonic society, already well organized? “Because it would be madness,” answers Johann Joachim Bode—their “Areopagite” for northern Germany, affiliated with the Order under the *nom de guerre* Amelius—“to play with open cards when the opponent keeps his hand hidden.” [1][5]

2. Method

This study employs an interdisciplinary and source-based approach, combining archival research, critical historiography, and musical analysis. The core of the investigation relies on unpublished documents and printed materials from the late eighteenth century, including ritual texts, correspondence, clandestine editions, and contemporary reports. Special attention is given to the role of musical sources—scores, librettos, and archival records—which are examined both as cultural artifacts and as vehicles for ideological transmission.

The methodology involves cross-referencing primary sources (letters, trial records, original prints, and musical manuscripts) with modern historiographical interpretations. Whenever possible, events and networks are reconstructed through direct evidence, avoiding speculative or sensationalist narratives. The analysis favors a comparative perspective, highlighting connections between the Illuminati network active in Valtellina and broader European movements (Freemasonry, radical Enlightenment, revolutionary societies).

Critical awareness is maintained throughout, with explicit recognition of the limitations posed by lost or censored sources, the secretive nature of the societies, and the risk of retrospective mythologization. The study aims to restore agency to often-neglected figures—printers, musicians, minor conspirators—placing them in the context of transnational cultural and political exchange.

3. Analysis

Against this unique background, the following sections analyze the formation, activities, and broader impact of Illuminati lodges in Valtellina and their connection to European intellectual networks.

3.0. Geographical and Historical Context

Due to its unique geographical position—nestled in the Central Alps of northern Italy, bordering Switzerland and Austria—and its political belonging to the “Three Leagues” (*Grisons* or *Grigioni*, an autonomous federation then under Swiss influence), Valtellina represented an exceptional setting for intellectual exchange at the end of the eighteenth century.

The region, stretching from the ancient city of Chiavenna through the valley and up to the county of Bormio, enjoyed comparatively greater freedom of the press and a more dynamic circulation of ideas, sheltered from the strict censorship that prevailed in neighboring Italian and Austrian territories. This particular environment made Valtellina the ideal location for the creation of illuminated Masonic lodges and for the dissemination of “dangerous” books and pamphlets inspired by the doctrines of Weishaupt and the Bavarian Illuminati.

3.1. Francesco Tommaso Maria De Bassus and the Poschiavo Printing Press

In Poschiavo—a small Alpine town in the Grisons (Grigioni) region, today just over the Swiss border but historically linked to Italy—an important clandestine printing press operated from 1780–81 on the estates of Baron Francesco Tommaso Maria De Bassus. [6]

De Bassus, a Freemason and Illuminatist known within the Order by the nom de guerre “Hannibal,” had also served as the podestà (magistrate) of Traona, a nearby town in Valtellina. The press was dedicated to the distribution, in Italian, of works originally written in German. De Bassus had brought the printer Giuseppe Ambrosioni from Bergamo to Poschiavo, and over about a decade of activity, they produced hundreds of editions. These publications, with the tacit cooperation of the Swiss postal system, circulated throughout northern Italy—especially in the Venetian Republic, which was connected to Valtellina via the San Marco Pass.

Some of the books printed in Poschiavo are still preserved today in the “Pio Rajna” library in Sondrio, the principal town of Valtellina. The *Galleria degli Antichi greci e romani* [7] was one of the few works produced by De Bassus that was not explicitly associated with revolutionary ideology. This volume, published in Poschiavo in 1783 by Giuseppe Ambrosioni, offered “a brief description” of the lives of ancient authors, “translated from German and dedicated to His Serene Highness Charles Frederick, Margrave of Baden and Hochberg.”

In the preface, after the dedication, De Bassus outlines the official and ostensible purpose of his press, “established in Poschiavo,” which was to make “the most noteworthy literary productions from beyond the Alps known to Italy, by having the best of them translated into the Tuscan language.” However, the majority of De Bassus’s editions demonstrate his engagement with and support for Weishaupt’s Illuminatist thought. Even this *Galleria*, seemingly innocuous, was aligned with the interests of the Order, since the Minervals were expected to meditate daily on the most eminent figures of ancient philosophy [8].

Among its most prestigious works, the Poschiavo printing house published in 1782 the first Italian translation of the novel *The Sorrows of Young Werther* by Johann Wolfgang Goethe, a Freemason affiliated with the Illuminati. During the years of *Werther*, the German poet was closely involved with Freemasons and wrote that their lodge was a most remarkable community. However, Goethe was not fully satisfied with the Freemasons, whom he regarded merely as a useful means to achieve his own aims: “because of that spirit of independence which later seemed to me a kind of madness,” the writer remarked, “I refused any closer ties.”

On June 23, 1780, Goethe was admitted to the Amalia Lodge in Weimar—a lodge under the influence of Adam Weishaupt and Johann Joachim Bode (1730–1793)—beginning at the rank of Apprentice. The following year, he was promoted to Fellow, and on March 2, 1782, he became a Master Mason. On December 4, he was granted

the Fourth Scottish Degree of Strict Observance, and on February 11, 1783, he signed the obligation as an Illuminatus, under the *nom de guerre* “Abaris.”

De Bassus had already traveled to Milan in 1781 to establish contacts with the writer Gaetano Grassi, who took charge of the Italian edition entitled *Werther / A Work of Sentiment / by Doctor Goethe / the Famous German Writer / Translated / by Gaetano Grassi / of Milan / With the Addition of an Apology in Favor of the Same Work*. Printed in Poschiavo by Giuseppe Ambrosioni, undated [February 2, 1782].

Because of its depiction of suicide [9], De Bassus’s edition was considered one of the works actively promoted by Weishaupt and was regarded as revolutionary and dangerous to Catholic morals at the time. The Bishop of Milan even ordered the purchase of all existing copies to remove it from circulation. Grassi’s translation is, in any case, an extraordinarily important typographical rarity from a historical perspective, as it became the most widespread Italian version between the late eighteenth and early nineteenth centuries. It was reprinted in Milan in 1800, in Basel and Livorno in 1808, in Florence that same year, and again in 1823.

The edition was dedicated to Jakob Hess, general superintendent of the Zurich postal system, which held the monopoly not only in Zurich, but also in Bern, St. Gallen, and Schaffhausen, as well as in Milan, Bergamo, and from there all the way to Venice.

The Poschiavo printing house also benefitted from the collaboration of the revolutionary Alberto De Simoni and the Illuminist from Trento, Carlantonio Pilati, who was affiliated under the *nom de guerre* “Lucrezio Caro.” The press also published his *Apology of the Freemasons*, attributed to brother ***, *a member of the ** Scottish lodge in P**. (Poschiavo, 1781) [10].

The Illuminati made strategic use of Masonic lodges and Freemasons as channels for spreading their radically libertarian ideas, which were far more extreme in their opposition to corrupt religious orders, tyranny, and the nobility.

3.2 The Illuminati in Valtellina: Context and Networks

Tommaso Maria De Bassus, the Areopagite responsible for Northern Italy, was highly active in creating a dense network of Illuminati lodges. In his report sent from **Traona** (a small town in the Valtellina valley) to the Areopagus on 25 February 1782, he mentions traveling to Milan, where he succeeded in affiliating Count Johann Joseph Wilczek, who would later become the Austrian plenipotentiary minister for Lombardy. De Bassus also operated in the **Engadine** (a high Alpine valley in what is now southeastern Switzerland) and extended the organization’s network to Tyrol, Trentino, the Veneto, and Valtellina itself. In Chiavenna—which appears under the code name Accaron [11], since even place names were concealed in the mysterious geography of the Order—a sizable lodge is thought to have existed, dependent on the Illuminatus known as Archimede. In June 1784, the Poschiavo baron writes from Bolzano: “I have made Archimede a Minerval, so that I can use him as secretary for the initiations at Accaron. He is a splendid man and will be of great use to the Order” [12].

A list of names and their respective lodges, compiled by De Bassus, shows the fervent proselytizing activity in various cities:

in Verona (Giovanni Battista de, M:d.L.; Alberto Albertini, merchant; Ferdinando Uberti; Count Giacomo Schioppo; Captain De Lagnes; Captain Nogarini; Anselmi, lawyer; Lazaro, Greek Jew; Isachetto, Greek Jew; Gi. Gius. Coen, Jew; Israd Coen, Jew),

in Vicenza (Captain Buon Augurio, M:L; Count Girolamo Tiene; Dr. Scola; Valentin Portinari, merchant; Pietro Belli; Crevell da Lion),

in Venice (Zini, lawyer, M:L.; Giuseppe Contin; Giuseppe Dell’Oglio; Dom Gasparini; Antonio Colombo; Captain Taroboccia; Dandolo, Venetian noble; Pietro Querini, Venetian noble; Ascanio Giustiniani, Venetian noble; Marquis Cessa; Count Pedemonte from Verona; Count Alessandro Calloti from Verona; Francesco Pedrini),

in Mantua (Major Gobboni; Don Giovanni Banieri; Manuele, Salomone, and Giacomo, the Franchetti brothers, Jews),

in Brescia (Orazio Sevali, Domenico Caldera),
in Bergamo (Count Alessandro Colebri),
in Milan (Sigl. Viaspoli; Joseph Wildzeck, Minister; Joseph Kinigl, Magistrate’s Councillor),
in Florence (Miller Obrister; Rosetta Major; Mr. Brunn; Fanaron, surgeon; Fenici, captain; Salvetti,
merchant; Manuele, Jew; Salvatore Finzi),
in Livorno (Mattiis, lieutenant; Della Ricca, Jew from Turin; Baron De Vieri; Sigl. Balmassa from Verona),
as well as in Cremona and Innsbruck. [12]

On January 24, 1787, Marquis Costanzo di Costanzo, who used the nom de guerre Diomede, wrote to Friedrich Münter, nom de guerre Syrianus: “In Italy, I know of only one important Superior, Baron von Bassus: he resides in the Grisons, at Poschiavo. If you pass through Switzerland and the detour is not too far out of your way, you should visit him; you will not regret having met such a worthy person”. [13]

The spread of Illuminist thought did not rely solely on the publication of books. Propaganda activities were the domain of the Minerval Academies—those literary and cultural circles that met periodically in the De Bassus residences in Poschiavo, Tirano, Morbegno, and Traona (all towns in the Valtellina valley). Here, participants would discuss literature, science, politics, philosophy, and art, and enjoy good music. Especially popular among the Illuminati were the satirical works targeting the Jesuits, known as *pasquiglie*—witty lampoons that amused the people at the expense of the clergy and religious truths. [14]

Weishaupt encouraged their publication, and De Bassus, in keeping with this, did not hesitate to include them among the editions he circulated throughout Valtellina.

3.3 Music, Satire, and Propaganda

Music, in its various forms—opera, instrumental, and ecclesiastical—also became a vehicle for Illuminist propaganda. From 1780 to 1788, about fifteen comic operas (*opere buffe*) were staged in Chiavenna and Sondrio, with as many as five performed in Sondrio during Carnival 1787. [15]

In addition to plot elements such as mistaken identities, dramatic twists, misunderstandings, and disguises, the librettos consistently offered themes of the lower classes gaining revenge over the frivolous, superficial, and overbearing nobility. At the time, comic opera was a fashionable form of entertainment, accessible even to smaller towns. Productions were far more streamlined and economical than those of serious opera and could be staged in the salons of noble residences or outdoors, in gardens and public squares.

Fra i due litiganti is an opera by Giuseppe Sarti that was staged in Sondrio during Carnival in 1787. The original libretto by Carlo Goldoni, entitled *Le Nozze*, was first set to music by Baldassare Galuppi and performed in Bologna in 1755. It was later revised by Giovanni Battista Lorenzi and then set to music by Gennaro Astarita under the title *Tra i due litiganti il terzo gode* (“While Two Quarrel, the Third Rejoices”). The version performed in Sondrio was based on the adaptation made by Sarti’s librettist for the La Scala production in 1782.

In the opera, the expectations of the nobility—represented by Count Belfiore (bass) and Countess Belfiore (soprano)—are inevitably disappointed. The victors are the maid and orphan Dorina (soprano) and the gardener Mingone (baritone), who are able to marry by outwitting the naïveté of their aristocratic masters.

Giuseppe Sarti (1729–1802) was also a Freemason and is believed to have been an Illuminatus. In this capacity, he was received in Vienna in the spring of 1784. At that time, he visited the Illuminati-affiliated lodge *Zur Wahren Eintracht* (“True Concord”), which was also frequented by Mozart. The lodge was led by the scientist and *Venerable Master* Ignaz von Born (*nom de guerre* Furius Camillus).

In Vienna, the lodge *Zur Wahren Eintracht* (“True Concord”) was the most important in the capital; another prominent lodge was *Zur Gekrönten Hoffnung* (“Crowned Hope”). The 1780s marked the period of greatest expansion for Illuminist Freemasonry. In 1784, there were 57 lodges in the Habsburg Empire, with 17 in Austria alone, according to official police sources—which were already suspicious of anti-monarchist infiltration and progressive ideas.

Mozart officially joined at the age of twenty-eight, on December 14, 1784, entering the small lodge *Zur Wohltätigkeit* (“Beneficence”), recruited by the Illuminatus Master Otto von Gemmingen (*nom de guerre* Antonius), a friend of the composer since their time in Mannheim. His lodge, too, was under the jurisdiction of Illuminatus von Born. In 1783, Gemmingen had been a guest of this distinguished scientist, delivering a speech in which he encouraged von Born to continue the fight “against the errors of mysticism.”

Mozart progressed through the ranks of the hierarchy, advancing from Apprentice to Fellow on January 7, 1785, and finally becoming a Master in the spring of that year. The composer was a regular attendee at lodge meetings, which were also held in other *officine* (Masonic lodges). For this reason, in order to avoid confusion, he signed his name with the full title of his lodge: *Mozart von der Wohltätigkeit* (“Mozart of Beneficence”). During his trip to Vienna in 1785, Leopold Mozart joined his son’s lodge, as he too was sympathetic to the Illuminati, having established excellent relations with the Illuminatus Freemason Wolfsegg, who had lent him money [16].

In June 1784, the Salzburg-born composer wrote a set of eight piano variations, K. 460, on a theme by Sarti, taken from the aria “Come un agnello” from the opera *Fra i due litiganti*, which had been performed in Sondrio. Mozart later reused this theme in the final scene of his *Don Giovanni*.

La Frascatana by Giovanni Paisiello (1740–1816), with a libretto by Filippo Livigni, was first staged in Venice in the autumn of 1774, then performed in Chiavenna in 1781 and in Sondrio during Carnival in 1787. The text is even more subversive toward nobles and clergymen. Giovanni Paisiello was affiliated with the Société Apollonienne, which was connected to the lodge *Les Neuf Sœurs* (“The Nine Sisters”) in Paris and closely aligned with Illuminatus ideas. According to Abbot Augustin Barruel, as he writes in his *Memoirs*, the two brothers Leopold and Joseph of Austria respectively controlled the Nine Sisters and Weishaupt’s Order in service of Empress Maria Theresa.

In *La Frascatana*, the nobleman is Cavaliere Giocondo (tenor), who travels to Velletri to marry his fiancée, Donna Stella (soprano). However, Stella, who is pursued by the despicable Don Fabrizio (bass), prefers the shepherd Nardone (tenor) over both foolish suitors—especially as, by the end of the opera, Nardone reveals himself to be an excellent match, inheriting four thousand sheep from his father.

The theme of marriage across social classes—a noble marrying a commoner—also features in other operas performed in Sondrio during Carnival in 1787 [17]. These include *Le nozze in contrasto* by Giovanni Valentini, with a libretto by Giovanni Bertati (1735–1815), first staged in Venice in 1779, and *L’Italiana in Londra*, an intermezzo in two parts composed by Domenico Cimarosa (1749–1801) in 1778, with a libretto by Giuseppe Petrosellini.

Cimarosa’s famous opera buffa *Giannina e Bernardone*, or *Il villano geloso*, with a libretto by Filippo Livigni, was written for the Teatro San Samuele in Venice in 1781 and had two productions in the province: the first in Chiavenna in 1784, the second in Sondrio in 1787. The story centers on the jealousy of Bernardone, the crude and irritable husband of Giannina. Around the couple move various characters of noble origin and loose morals, such as Captain Francone, who, despite being engaged to Donna Aurora, does not hesitate to fall in love with Lauretta, Bernardone’s sister. Giannina, in contrast, demonstrates her moral integrity and remains faithful to her husband despite an infatuation with Don Orlando, Aurora’s uncle. In an effort to placate the quarrelsome Bernardone—who is mocked and mistreated by everyone—poor Giannina resorts even to faking her own suicide. Naturally, the opera ends happily, with the couple reconciling and promising each other love and understanding.

3.4 Johann Simon Mayr and the First Operatic Werther

The year 1787 was thus a significant one for musical life in Sondrio, coinciding with the arrival in Poschiavo and Valtellina—at the service of Baron De Bassus—of the Bavarian musician Johann Simon Mayr.

Mayr was born on June 14, 1763, in Mendorf, a small village in the Danube region of Bavaria, near Ingolstadt. As a youth, after his voice changed, he taught himself to play string and wind instruments. Lacking a regular teacher, he was instructed in musical practice by his father, Joseph Mayr (1738–1807), who was the organist in Mendorf. In the autumn of 1769, he was sent to study music at the monastery of Weltenburg, where he remained until 1771. He entered the Jesuit College of Ingolstadt, a city where, thanks to the patronage of Tommaso Maria De Bassus and Adam Weishaupt, he attended university courses.

Mayr was admitted to the Order of the Illuminati under the *nom de guerre* Aristotile [18] and, in 1778, was registered among the students of rhetoric and logic; from 1780 to 1784 he attended courses in medicine, and from 1784 to 1785, courses in law. His abandonment of his studies in 1785 coincided with the expulsion from Ingolstadt of students suspected of Illuminatism, following the persecutions initiated by the Elector of Bavaria against Weishaupt's followers.

De Bassus kept the young composer with him from 1787 to 1789, both to introduce him to German music and to strengthen the Illuminist musical movement in the Grisons and northern Italy. The Poschiavo Academy had been replicated in Sondrio, likely in a noble residence, and probably also in Chiavenna at the Salis Palace—a family to whom Baron De Bassus was closely connected.

From the De Bassus residence, Mayr supervised musical life throughout the Grisons region. Following the advice in Weishaupt's statutes, he began by seeking influence over places of worship, composing masses and sacred music, for example, for the Basilica Madonna di Tirano. [19]

Meanwhile, he frequented the De Bassus–Ambrosioni printing house, applying himself to the challenge of transforming that first Italian translation of Goethe's novel into an Illuminist musical work. He would complete this endeavor around 1794 in Venice, with the creation of a one-act comic opera (*farsa*) entitled *Verter*. This first *Werther* in operatic form (the earlier work by Gaetano Pugnani in 1790 is a *melologo*—a spoken drama accompanied by instrumental music) is also Mayr's first opera, composed to a libretto by Simeone Antonio Sografi (1759–1818). *Verter* has been entirely neglected by scholars: it is not listed among Mayr's works, not even in the most comprehensive musical encyclopedias, such as Grove, MGG, or DEUMM.

Under the mistaken title *Werther e Carlotta*, Mayr's opera has, for years, been considered a variant of the *farsa Labino e Carlotta* [20], composed in 1799.

We discovered Mayr's *Verter* in 1994 [21] and prepared a critical edition [22] for the 1995–1996 symphonic season at the Teatro Donizetti in Bergamo, where only the opera's Symphony was performed on that occasion. [23]

The complete work, later recorded on CD, received its world premiere at the Rossini Festival in Wildbad in 2001 and was also staged that same year in Poschiavo. At the Wildbad roundtable, we presented our findings on the connections with *The Magic Flute*, along with the history of De Bassus's printing house and its links to the Bavarian Illuminati. During a lecture at Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań, we explored further thematic links with *The Magic Flute* and demonstrated how Mayr reused characteristic motifs from his other compositions, weaving them into *Verter*. In that same lecture, we also recounted this remarkable chapter in cultural and political history, emphasizing the clandestine activities of the Bavarian Illuminati's printing press in Poschiavo. In April 2025, *Verter* was revived at the Beethoven Festival in Warsaw at the National Philharmonic and was again recorded for CD release.

A second manuscript of *Verter* survives in the Austrian National Library in Vienna, attributed to Vincenzo Puccita, alongside a printed libretto published in Venice in 1802 under the name of Domenico Camagna. These later versions differ from the Milan manuscript both musically and structurally: Puccita simplifies and shortens certain sections, especially Carlotta's virtuosic passages, while Camagna's libretto further departs from

Sografi's refined language. The division of scenes also shifts significantly between versions, confirming that Puccita's and Camagna's adaptations are nineteenth-century reworkings intended for new performers. [24]

We have transcribed and revised the entire Milan score. The Milan manuscript, remarkable for its inventiveness, remains the primary and authentic source for Mayr's *Verter*, and served as the basis for the performances at Wildbad, Poschiavo, and Warsaw. The opera contains unmistakable "Mayrian" themes, also found in his symphonies, concertos, and oratorios such as *Sisara*.

Although *Verter* is an early composition, its music is fascinating—masterfully constructed, rich in harmonic and contrapuntal effects, and featuring Rossinian crescendos that anticipate the style of Rossini by two decades.

The plot of *Verter* is quite straightforward. As in Goethe's epistolary novel, the young protagonist falls in love with the beautiful Carlotta, who is married to Alberto, and is torn between his desire for her and his loyalty to friendship. Giorgio, an additional character—possibly a cleric or Jesuit—plays an active role, seeking to discredit Verter and Carlotta in Alberto's eyes. However, Verter receives help from his servant Ambrogio and the maid Paolina. Together, they help the protagonist prove his innocence and Carlotta's fidelity, prevent his suicide, and unmask the treacherous Giorgio. [25]

What is particularly remarkable is Mayr's bold and systematic approach to *Verter*, where he transforms and integrates musical material from Mozart's *The Magic Flute* with both erudition and dramatic flair. *Verter* stands as the first Masonic–Illuminatist interpretation of Mozart's celebrated opera: Mayr overturns prevailing theories and offers a new interpretative key to Goethe's own sequel, *The Magic Flute, Part Two (Der Zauberflöte zweiter Teil)*, a little-known dramatic work in which Goethe continues the story begun by Mozart.

We have analyzed these connections in detail in our book on Mozart's *Magic Flute*. The relationships between De Bassus, Goethe, Mozart, and Mayr are discussed extensively in our volume *Goethe, Mozart e Mayr: Fratelli illuminati* (Milan, Arché, 2001), later expanded and translated into English as *Goethe, Mozart, and Mayr: Illuminati Brothers* (Lecce, Youcanprint, 2025).

The activities of the Poschiavo printing house appear to come to an abrupt halt, as did performances of comic operas in Valtellina and Valchiavenna, after 1788. Following the Bavarian police persecutions, the Order of the Illuminati was declared illegal, and many leading members were arrested and put under investigation. Baron De Bassus had his castle at Sandersdorf in Bavaria seized, where police discovered numerous documents belonging to Weishaupt's secret Order. De Bassus narrowly escaped financial ruin; in order to regain his property, he was forced to renounce the Illuminati, swear loyalty to Elector Karl Theodor of Bavaria, and publicly defend himself before the Tribunal of the Three Leagues. Despite having been the highest-ranking figure in the Italian District, in his *Esposizione presented to the Most Illustrious Leaders of the Eminent Republic of the Grisons*, printed in Poschiavo in 1787, De Bassus declared that he held no important position within the Order.

The printer Ambrosioni, for his part, left Valtellina and returned permanently to Bergamo. In reality, however, neither of the two ever truly abandoned their Illuminatist mission.

3.5 The Spezieria of Sondrio

In northern Italy, from 1790 to 1791, a revolutionary and destabilizing gazette—of the type encouraged by Weishaupt—continued to be circulated under the title *Appendice politica a tutte le gazzette e altri foglietti di novità ossia la Spezieria di Sondrio in Valtellina presso i Grigioni, Anno Primo, 1789, Anno Secondo, 1790* (*Political Appendix to All the Gazettes and Other News Sheets, or the Apothecary's Shop of Sondrio in Valtellina, Near the Grisons, First Year, 1789, Second Year, 1790*). [26]

“It was 1789, and it was then that a peculiar mind in that very year brought the society frequenting the Spezieria of Sondrio—a unique public refuge for the local chatter of Sondrio—into political conversation. It was a symposium in which the news of the day was reviewed and commented on in light of prevailing doctrines.” The interlocutors, in addition to the editor Lazzaro Jona, included a former Jesuit, a Prussian officer, and an abbot. “The author or authors took great care to maintain secrecy, for reasons that were all too reasonable at the time. Mr. Balsamo, the apothecary, is one of the principal participants in these political dialogues”. [27]

This dialogic journal took as its model the Masonic *Café politique d'Amsterdam*, opposed feudal, aristocratic, and militaristic privileges, championed freedom of the press and the Third Estate, and exalted the liberal, democratic, and even radical positions of the American and French revolutions, as represented by Franklin and Mirabeau. The list of topics treated in 1789 included, in addition to politics, economics, medicine, and law. In 1789, Sondrio—still under Grisons (Swiss) rule—was shielded from police investigations.

According to Cesare Cantù, “that gazette was not printed in Sondrio, but in Cremona”. [28]

In that city as well, the lodges had previously been illuminated by De Bassus: “If Areopagite Hannibal [De Bassus] has less hope for Milan, where there are no Masonic lodges, he writes that he will surely find them in Cremona and Pavia and throughout the rest of Italy. He therefore requests that the Geographical Dictionary be expanded to include these cities, for the conquests he hopes to make there”. [29]

The Sondrio scholar Battista Leoni, based on research conducted at the State Archive of Modena, suggests that the author of the *Spezieria* was Giovanni Ristori and that the revolutionary weekly was printed with a false date in Modena. [30]

Renato Sòriga, on the other hand, attributes the *Spezieria* to the presses of the Poschiavo printing house. [31]

Franco Venturi tends to identify the so-called Lazzaro Jona, the journal's editor, with Baron De Bassus himself, who would have assumed that Hebrew name—just as Filippo Buonarroti used the pseudonym Abraham Levi Salomon when writing the *Giornale Patriottico* in Corsica. The Swiss scholar and historian Massimo Lardi sees in Lazzaro Jona a resurrected De Bassus, a prophet “resuscitated” and surviving “in the belly of the whale” after the trial he faced before the Tribunal of the Three Leagues. Carlo Francovich asserts that the gazette “certainly was not printed in Sondrio, since no local historian nor any repertory records it, and it should therefore be attributed without doubt to De Bassus and his collaborators: Ambrosioni, De Simoni, and Pilati”. [32]

3.6 Mayr and Ambrosioni

Marino Berengo describes the Poschiavo printer Giuseppe Ambrosioni as “a man of openly Jacobin sympathies”. [33]

According to Luigi Santini, the two booksellers Rondi and Ambrosioni played an important role in importing prohibited books into the Bergamo area and northern Italy. In 1791, the city of Bergamo was governed by the *podestà* and the *capitano*, who collaborated with inquisitors active in Venice. The Republic of Venice had remained neutral in French affairs, specifically to hinder revolutionary political propaganda. These authorities monitored newspapers, and any printed materials deemed dangerous that came from abroad or from France, often containing in full the speeches of the National Assembly. Under the term “gazettes” were often hidden pamphlets on the revolution.

The director of the Swiss postal service [34] was supposed to withhold prohibited gazettes destined for Bergamo. In October 1791, the rectors of Bergamo reassured the inquisitors by censoring comic and tragic theatrical works “in order to keep from subjects the poison of modern maxims of liberty and independence.” The *Vicario pretorio* was charged with examining such works for anything contrary to religion or public morality.

The inquisitors were aware of the “pernicious” books being secretly introduced into Bergamo and instructed the *Podestà* “to take an active but prudent interest in discovering which of the Bergamo printing houses might be involved and whether they were attempting to send copies beyond the borders of the state.” On 14 April 1792, the rectors reported that “the safest and most effective means have been used to ascertain whether this merchant Ambrosioni has imported and sells works contrary to religion and good politics, especially the one entitled *The Rights of Man* by Abbot Spedalieri, the periodical papers from Sondrio [35], and the like. However, it seems that the said Ambrosioni is completely ignorant of Spedalieri’s work and has never even seen the indicated periodical”. [36]

At one point, a crate of books arrived for Ambrosioni, which the authorities could not open because it was addressed to a destination outside the territory of the republic. Ambrosioni was required to provide documentation proving that the crate was indeed intended for export. Nonetheless, the authorities in Bergamo remained suspicious of him, not without reason, as he was always actively involved in political life and would become one of the protagonists of the 1797 uprisings.

Already in May 1795, a French work entitled *Le passe par tout de l’Eglise Romaine*, which collected maxims contrary to religion and public morals, had been confiscated from Giuseppe Ambrosioni. [37]

Giuseppe Ambrosioni, friend of Baron De Bassus and the musician Johann Simon Mayr, former printer and bookseller, became General Administrator of the Finance Chamber in Bergamo in 1797, following the expulsion of the Austrians. He sought to alleviate the needs of the population and public charities. On his proposal, a decree of 21 May abolished all taxes on oils, both domestic and foreign. The following day, in order to provide a stable foundation for the city’s almshouse, the municipality assigned it the assets of the monasteries that had been suppressed, to increase the income of the main hospital (*Ospedale Maggiore*).

Taking advantage of Enlightenment principles of communal ownership, the Civic Library of Bergamo was also enriched, as the volumes from monastic collections became property of the city. These measures, which affected the highly influential clerical class, aroused significant discontent and strong opposition.

In 1797, Ambrosioni also served as administrator of the District of Bergamo: “On 5 August, the administration of the district was assumed by the citizens Vincenzo Spini, Carlo Ribier, Giuseppe Ambrosioni, Luigi Cavalli, Cesare Cavalier, Antonio Vallaperta, Pietro Maffeis, Gaetano Carminati, Cristoforo Scotti, and Gerolamo Adelasio, appointed by Bonaparte”. [38]

There was also an extraordinary police commission, among whose members was Count Pietro Pesenti—possibly related to Canon Vincenzo Pesenti, the Bergamasque patron of Mayr.

Ambrosioni's career was far from over: in 1797, he served as a member of the Council of Elders (*Consiglio dei Seniori*) of the Cisalpine Republic [39], and in 1805, he became president of the Municipality of Bergamo. [40]

A letter from Mayr, sent from Venice, survives in which the composer thanks Ambrosioni for his appointment as Maestro di Cappella. It was also Ambrosioni who hosted Mayr for a time in Bergamo and, through his connections, introduced him to Canon Vincenzo Pesenti, who would later become Mayr's patron. [41]

At the end of the eighteenth century, in Valtellina—a decade little studied from a historical perspective but essential for understanding the spread of principles of equality and freedom—music and theatrical performances (from 1780 to 1790) served as vehicles of propaganda. These were orchestrated or supported by the most liberal currents of thought, by Freemasonry, and by the Bavarian Illuminati, who wielded considerable influence in this region.

Traces of their activity survive in the *Fondo Antico* of the “Pio Rajna” Library in Sondrio, which contains rare works by Weishaupt, De Bassus, De Simoni, Pilati, Knigge, and books by anti-Masonic historians—theorists of a conspiracy against states and religions—such as those by Barruel. Two editions (1797 and 1802) of the *Memoirs* of Abbot Augustin Barruel are preserved there, demonstrating the intense local interest in a sect that had made Valtellina one of its strongholds. From this outpost, “Hannibal” (De Bassus) would spread the new Illuminatist ideas to the rest of Italy.

4. Limitations

Research on clandestine societies and secret networks inevitably encounters obstacles arising from the scarcity and fragmentary nature of surviving sources. Many documents were intentionally destroyed, falsified, or never recorded, making definitive reconstruction hazardous. The reliance on anti-Masonic or polemical writings introduces the risk of distortion and ideological bias. Furthermore, the persistent tendency to mythologize the Illuminati—especially in later historiography—complicates the task of distinguishing historical fact from conspiracy theory. Where documentation is missing or ambiguous, this paper adopts a cautious and critical stance, privileging verifiable evidence over speculation.

Additionally, the political and religious climate of the era fostered both deliberate disinformation and fertile ground for retrospective mythmaking. This article consciously avoids sensationalism, favoring documented facts over conjecture. As always with the history of the Illuminati, the central challenge remains to separate fact from the kind of fantasy that now proliferates on conspiracy blogs and popular culture.

Notes

- [1] Augustin Barruel, *Mémoires pour servir à l'histoire du jacobinisme* (London, 1797), 4 vols. (Second edition, with additions and Italian translation: Lyon, 1802, 5 vols.).
- [2] John Robison, *Proofs of a Conspiracy against all the Religions and Governments of Europe, carried on in the Secret Meetings of Free Masons, Illuminati, and Reading Societies. Collected from Good Authorities, by John Robison, A.M., Professor of Natural Philosophy, and Secretary to the Royal Society of Edinburgh* (Edinburgh, 1797; reprint: Boston and Los Angeles, Western Islands, 1967).
- [3] John Robison, *op. cit.*, p. 9: “The Order of the Illuminati took its first rise among the Free Masons but is totally different from Free Masons. It was not, however, the mere protection gained by the secrecy of the Lodges that gave occasion to it, but it arose naturally from the corruptions that had gradually crept into that fraternity, the violence of the party-spirit which pervaded it, and from the total uncertainty and darkness that hangs over the whole of that mysterious association.”
- [4] For clarity, “Illuminatism” refers specifically to the doctrines and practices of the Illuminati and should not be confused with Enlightenment philosophy.
- [5] The Areopagite was, within the Order, the head of a District, responsible for a wide geographical area; all the leading figures formed the Areopagus.
- [6] Valuable information on De Bassus and the Poschiavo printing house can be found in Massimo Lardi’s preface to Johann Wolfgang Goethe, *I dolori del giovane Werther* (Coira: Pro Grigioni Italiano, 2001), and in Luca Bianchini and Anna Trombetta, “Il Verter di Mayr e i legami col De Bassus e l’ambiente culturale, politico e illuminato di Poschiavo,” *Quaderni Grigionitaliani* (Coira: Pro Grigioni Italiano, 2000).
- [7] Two copies are preserved at the “Pio Rajna” Library in Sondrio, catalogued as G III 766 and A IV 296.
- [8] Regarding the instruction for the Minerval degree, the Weishaupt code states: “In the following class, I plan to establish a kind of literary academy. I want the study of the ancients, the art of observing and outlining historical characters—and those of living persons—and the gathering of treatises and proposed questions, to form the occupation of our students here...”. See Agostino Barruel, *Storia del Giacobinismo. Massoneria e Illuminati di Baviera* (preface by Alberto Cesare Ambesi), Carmagnola: Arktos Oggero Editore, 1989, p. 173.
- [9] On the symbolic meaning of suicide, see Luca Bianchini and Anna Trombetta, *Goethe, Mozart, Mayr: Illuminati Brothers* (Lecce: Youcanprint, 2025).
- [10] The *Apologia*, of which a copy is also preserved in the Fondo Antico of the “Pio Rajna” Library in Sondrio (catalogue B III 1153), was published anonymously and has been attributed by Remo Bornatico to the Illuminatus from Trentino, Carantonio Pilati. See Remo Bornatico, *L’arte tipografica nella Tre Leghe (1547–1803) e nei Grigioni (1803–1975)* (Chur: Edizione propria, 1976), p. 61.
- [11] The Illuminati used code names not only for their affiliates, but also for cities, states, and regions. They also made use of cryptography and the ancient Persian calendar to indicate days and months of the year.
- [12] Carlo Francovich, *Albori socialisti nel Risorgimento. Contributo allo studio delle società segrete (1776–1835)* (Florence: Le Monnier, 1962), p. 62.
- [13] Carlo Francovich, *op. cit.*, p. 75.
- [14] Original writings, letters of 15 February 1778 and 4 April 1779, quoted in Agostino Barruel, *Storia del Giacobinismo. Massoneria e Illuminati di Baviera, op. cit.*, p. 176.
- [15] See Fabio Sartorelli and Paolo Raineri, “L’opera buffa a Chiavenna nel Settecento,” in *Clavenna, Bollettino del centro di studi storici valchiavennaschi*, Year XXXVI, 1997.

[16] For a comprehensive overview of Mozart's Masonic initiation and Illuminati path, even during his years in Salzburg, see Luca Bianchini and Anna Trombetta, *Mozart: The Magic Flute* (Lecce: Youcanprint, 2018).

[17] See *Un almanacco drammatico. L'indice de' Teatrali Spettacoli 1764–1823*, edited by R. Verti (Pesaro: Fondazione Rossini, 1996).

[18] As hypothesized by the scholar John Stewart Allitt. See John Stewart Allitt, "An Introduction to the Study of Mayr's Life," in *Beiträge des 1. Internationalen Simon-Mayr-Symposiums vom 2. bis 4. Oktober 1992 in Ingolstadt* (Ingolstadt: Donaukurier Verlag, 1995).

[19] Mayr's biographer Girolamo Calvi writes that during his stay in Valtellina, the composer "also produced a Mass and Vespers for the annual solemn celebration at the renowned Sanctuary of the Madonna di Tirano." It is by no means certain that this refers to the *Messa breve a tre* in C major, for soprano, tenor, and bass, with obbligato organ and small orchestra. The score survives undated and without indication of place. Composed perhaps in 1787, the Mass was performed again in modern form, over two centuries later, on October 15, 1999, for the anniversary of the Apparition, and presented to the public as if it had certainly been composed for the Madonna di Tirano.

[20] See John Stewart Allitt, *J. S. Mayr Father of 19th Century Italian Music* (Shaftesbury: Element Books, 1989), p. 176. The farsa *Labino e Carlotta* has nothing in common with Goethe's novel and is based on a different story. This erroneous cataloguing is also found in John Stewart Allitt, *Giovanni Simone Mayr, Vita musica pensiero*, Italian translation by Sergio Pagliaroli, revised by Sandra Benigna and Giuliana Donati Petteni (Villa di Serio (Bg): Edizioni Villadiseriane, 1995), p. 377. Allitt confirms that *Labino e Carlotta*, *Sabino e Carlotta*, and *Werther e Carlotta* are the same comic farsa, performed at the Teatro di San Benedetto in Venice in 1799.

[21] For details on the discovery, see Luca Bianchini and Anna Trombetta, *Goethe, Mozart, and Mayr: Illuminati Brothers*, with a preface by Alberto Basso (Lecce: Youcanprint, 2025).

[22] Early works cannot be performed as found; they must be restored, revised, and corrected, and transcribed into modern musical notation. This is a rather long and complex process, which today is carried out entirely by computer.

[23] The Symphony of *Verter* was published online on the historic site italianOpera.org in 1996 and, at that time, could be listened to at www.novanet.it/bianchini. Please note that Novanet no longer exists and the link is no longer functional.

[24] For a comparison between the two works, see Luca Bianchini and Anna Trombetta, *Goethe, Mozart, and Mayr: Illuminati Brothers* (Lecce: Youcanprint, 2025).

[25] The full libretto of *Verter*, with our introduction, is published in Luca Bianchini and Anna Trombetta, *Goethe, Mozart, e Mayr, fratelli illuminati*, with a preface by Alberto Basso (Milan: Arké, 2009).

[26] An incomplete copy of the first volume (1789) is preserved in the "Pio Rajna" Library in Sondrio, in the Valtellina collection.

[27] Anonymous article in two installments on the *Spezieria di Sondrio*, published in the weekly *Valtellina*, November 15 and 22, 1862.

[28] Cesare Cantù, *Storia della città e diocesi di Como* (Florence, 1856), vol. II, p. 240.

[29] Original writings, vols. I and II, the four letters of Annibale, cited in Augustin Barruel, *Mémoires...*, *op. cit.*, vol. IV.

- [30] See Battista Leoni, *L'Appendice politica a tutte le gazzette e altri foglietti di novità, La Spezieria di Sondrio (1789–90) e il suo compilatore* (Sondrio: Chamber of Commerce, 1962), p. 9.
- [31] The copy of the *Gazzetta* preserved in the Museo del Risorgimento in Milan, Bertarelli Collection no. 15175, is catalogued with Sòriga's note: "The newspaper, which was weekly, was perhaps printed in Chur or Poschiavo."
- [32] Carlo Francovich, *Albori socialisti nel Risorgimento. Contributo allo studio delle società segrete (1776–1835)* (Florence: Le Monnier, 1962), p. 82.
- [33] Marino Berengo, *Società veneta alla fine del Settecento* (Florence, 1956).
- [34] Hans Jakob Hess had left in 1788.
- [35] This very likely refers to *Appendice politica a tutte le gazzette e altri foglietti di novità ossia la Spezieria di Sondrio, in Valtellina presso i Grigioni*, Anno Primo, 1789, Anno Secondo, 1790.
- [36] Bortolo Belotti, *Storia di Bergamo e dei Bergamaschi* (Milan: Ceschina, 1940), vol. II, p. 616.
- [37] Bortolo Belotti, *op. cit.*, vol. II, p. 633.
- [38] Bortolo Belotti, *op. cit.*, vol. III, p. 55.
- [39] Bortolo Belotti, *op. cit.*, vol. III, p. 73.
- [40] Bortolo Belotti, *op. cit.*, vol. III, p. 89.
- [41] Arrigo Gazzaniga, *Giovanni Simone Mayr. Passi scelti dallo Zibaldone e altri scritti* (Bergamo: Bolis, 1993), pp. 13–14.

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